

Design of Social Media Websites Acting as a Product of User's Virtual Needs and Expectations

Muhammad Yousaf Mushtaq
The Superior College,
Pakistan.
yousafsindhu@gmail.com

Muhammad Salman Mushtaq
The University of Queensland,
Australia.
m.mushtaq@uqconnect.edu.au

Muhammad Waseem Iqbal
The Superior College,
Pakistan.
waseem.iqbal@superior.edu.pk

Syeda Mehwish Jamil
National Institute of Psychology,
Pakistan.
Syedamehwish91@gmail.com

Abstract— Social networking sites (SNSs) are one of the most widely used means of communication. For a productive and practical design of social media websites, two factors are critical; to know the psyche of the user, and to be able to foresee the latent needs while developing a design or feature of social media. As the use of social media such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Myspace are increasing with the rapid growth especially in mobile users, there are many theories describing the interplay of virtual needs and user expectations in web designing. Social media is not used for communication only but also for the sake of playing a part in society, satisfying the need for social acceptance, the realisation of one's self and form associations with a particular group of people. This study provides a detailed overview of different theories and models that discuss the inherent properties of social media platforms and explains the different observations that result from the interplay of these factors.

Keywords; SNSs; Human Behavior; Social Media

I. INTRODUCTION

Social networking websites and applications are firmly integrated into modern users' life. The modern user not only interacts via these media tools but also gets the latest updates on unique and innovative methods of interaction, self-presentation, and communication [1]. Social media use has changed significantly over the last ten years. Now the social media platforms like Facebook, Myspace and Instagram and Twitter provide the user with a multitude of services. These services include building the users' profile, sharing the messages and images and videos and forming groups and associations with other user members of the social media platform. The user can do all that because of the functions inherently designed and ingrained to the architecture of social media platforms [2] [3]. With the such an accelerating pace of growth, Facebook reaches 2.4 billion users, annual revenue of Twitter comes up to \$2.53 billion marks and number of daily active users worldwide, by the end of 2020, is expected to surpass 3 billion [4].

The use of social media, in the contemporary age, has changed our lives to a great extent. Examples include New York Times, one of the most famous newspapers, hiring a social media manager [5]; and the former Governor of California, Arnold Schwarzenegger, keeping more than 4.4 million followers on Twitter, and social media marketing is considered among one of the highest financially rewarding jobs [6]; this journey is extraordinary. Jonathan and Steve define social media as a "technological tool for better communication" [7]. Qualman proposes the same argument by saying, "Social media is not a fad; it is a fundamental shift in the way we communicate" [8]. Simply put, the objective of, almost all, social media platforms are to communicate [9].

However, social media is not all about just communication at a personal level. SNSs are responsible for enabling the user to voice their concerns regarding society, political system and general global culture to a great extent. Research by Jeong and Lee analysed the effects of social media websites on the intention of the user in terms of joining a cause (like social) and found that social media websites are more likely to increase the users' intentions as compared to other means of publicity (ads, pamphlets) [10].

This paper is an attempt to analyse social media platforms and their design. In addition to that this paper investigates if the innovativeness in the designing the functions and services of the platform causes an increase in user base or if the users, themselves, manage to urge the social media platform owners and designers to create, innovate and improve by their repetitive usage of certain features of the platform. To summarise, this research has two main aims; one, provide an understanding towards the psychological framework for the use of social media; two, point out the social media functions that play a part in attracting a user.

In a review paper, Ngai, Moon and Chin presented a conceptual framework in order to explain the mechanism by which the social media platforms are supported by different tools and set of technologies that have a direct correlation with the personal and social behaviour of the user [11]. This study

proposed that users, internet-based tools, and technologies provide the basis of social media platforms.

It also pointed out that the processes of communication through social media is the “realisation of interaction”, inherently, between different users. There are different systems of information at play here, and Gregor classifies the relevant theories in the context of information systems. He proposes; theory for description and analysis that explains, what the information system is?; theory for understanding that explains, how and why this information system is built?; theory for predicting that explains what will happen with that information?; and theory for design and action that explains how to do stuff [12].

In the following section, some theories are discussed that analyse the psychological dimensions of social media. There are some models and theories that focus on the phenomenon of users accepting technology and different tools used in that. These theories and their models explain how a social media platform finds associations with the needs of the social media user. In the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) model, Fishbein and Ajzen proposed that users would use the technological tools if they can observe their benefits [13].

This model simply implies that for any use of technological tools, the user should be able to observe the benefits of social media. According to TPB, Theory of Planned Behaviour, there is a skill set required to use the technological tools, and the existence of that skill set is a critical factor for a user to tend using the technology tools [14].

A. Literature Review

It is important to analyse different uses of social media so a better understanding can be developed as to why and how people are attracted to social media platforms.

According to Jonathan and Steve, social media can be defined by its uses. According to them, “social media is a technology tool based on computer-mediation, having foundations in Web 2.0 applications, enabling the communication of information and ideas” [7]. Though the terms like “computer-mediation” and “web 2.0” are technical therefore the user is least likely to know about them, even while using the social media platforms. Nevertheless, from the perspective of the social media user, “multimodal set of actors” seems to be a domain that can be explored in detail. At this point, a key question surfaces if these multimodal actors are intertwined with the virtual needs and want of the social media user?

From the marketing point of view, it is required to know which need of consumer or user is of the utmost importance. There are specific standards devised by the market researchers and consumer behaviour specialists that provide a helping hand in understanding the needs and wants of a technology user. Hallikainen derived functions, from Seth’s Theory of Consumption, for the use of social media, which satisfies user needs and adds specific values. These functions are described in TABLE I.

TABLE I. HALLIKAINEN’S SOCIAL MEDIA FUNCTIONS

Value Category	Acquired Function
Functional Value	The ability of SNSs to provide means to achieve one’s goals
Social Value	The accession of a set of social values from social groups association
Emotional Value	Experience of emotional arousal by experiencing enjoyment
Epistemic Value	The ability of social media to provide the user with curiosity and deliver knowledge
Conditional Value	Add value to certain conditions such as planning, inviting and celebrating on birthdays

The model provided by Hallikainen focuses on the uses of social media, and it can be safely concluded that social media provides all these needs to a large extent. For example, Sheldon reviewed hierarchy of needs by Maslow and proposed that the need for pleasure-stimulation is one of the ten most basic human needs. The pleasure-stimulation can be defined as “the feeling that you get plenty of enjoyment and pleasure rather than feeling bored and under-stimulated by life” [15]. Ellison and Steinfield did their research in the same footsteps, conducted research, and proposed that use of Facebook is a source of pleasure for its users [16].

Some researchers have used Uses and Gratification Theory to better understand the needs of the user [17]. The gratification is related to the user’s identity, and identity is an essential part of self-concept [18]. It means, to simply put, one is aware of what one thinks about one’s self? [19]. Generally, the concept of self maintains the question “Who am I?” [20]. While seeking the gratification, people attempt to get comfort, pleasure, and social acceptance. To understand the architecture of the reason and design behind social networking platforms, we can discuss any of these needs. Two researchers, Papacharissi and Mendelson, devised factor analysis to calculate the following scales of motivation levels for using Facebook:

- Facebook is a source of amusement
- A platform to share information
- A source of providing pastime activities
- Manage the social interactions

Needs and requirements of the user define the design and development of modern social media platforms [21]. These needs and requirements take the shape of the values, and these values elaborate on the psychological preferences of the social media user and their ideas. This phenomenon incites the functions, features, and uses of social media websites and applications. It also highlights what is essential for them [22]. Krishen and Agarwal have identified and discussed constructs and interactivity modules mentioned in Table II while working in the same domain of research [23].

Table II. KRISHEN AND AGARWAL’S INTERACTIVITY MODULES

Construct	Items
Belonging [24]	I am a proud member of __
	I like being a part of __
	I have a strong sense of association for __
Interactivity [25]	My thought process is affected by the users __
	I can influence the users on __
	Members of __ think my opinion is important

	I care about what members of ___ think about my act
Affinity [26]	I think my social and recreational needs are satisfied on ___
	I can get help on ___ in case I need help,
	Being a part of ___ is worth my time
	Users on ___ care for me
Emotional connection [25]	I think members on ___ platform understand me well
	I get the feeling of closeness on ___
	I get along well with the users of ___
	I think the user members on ___ are friendly towards me
Satisfaction [24]	Use of the ___ helps me to satiate my need for information
	I feel satisfied with the online web community of ___
	My social needs are satisfied with the online community on ___
	My participation in ___ was a satisfying experience
Innovativeness [27]	I love to take chances
	I like to experiment with innovative methods of performing things
	I like new products because they are usually gimmicks

It is justified to conclude that the constructs discussed above are the focal point of users' philosophy towards the use of social media platforms. In user's thought processes, user satisfies the need for social interaction by using social media websites as Hanjun and Robert reported [28], and the information-seeking quest of the user is also accomplished [29]. Social media is satisfying the boredom and providing a pass time [30], supplying entertainment [30] and creating a sense of utility [31].

II. METHODOLOGY

The implications of the design and functions of social media have already been discussed; however, what is the design/functionality of social media exactly? Jan, Silvestre, and McCarthy presented a honeycomb model. According to them, everything that the social media designers and developers offer resides in this honeycomb model [6].

Figure 1. Jan, Silvestre and McCarthy's honeycomb model

The second block, conversation, is also an important one that includes options such as like and dislike, "subscribe" or "follow" the page of group/person or entity. A fine example is of Twitter that is designed for writing up small messages, and all of them are real-time "status updates" [33]. This is the way users have a conversation, share and receive information.

Sharing of the information implies the expanse to which the social media user exchanges and spreads various forms of data that might include texts, pictures, videos. Being part of the matrix, the user considers about sharing the ideas in different forms, and functionality like sharing a picture or video; to satisfies this condition [6].

The block presence represents "the extent to which users can know if other users are accessible" [6]. Social media applications offer this functionality based on geographical specifications. Many websites offer the user to share their geo-location in the form of status or status updates, venue check-ins and places they have recently visited. The platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Gowalla even show friends who are in the vicinity of the user. The relationship building is another block, that shows how much the user can affiliate with others. A sufficient instance is of the relationship building by sending "friend requests" on Facebook.

Having or belonging to a group is also an essential part of the matrix. It shows the extent to which a user can engage in the groups, clubs, and communities available online. Robin Dunbar, the renowned anthropologist, suggested that a person, on average, can have a maximum of one hundred and fifty social relationships [34] [35]. On the contrary, social media designers and developers identified that to be false and suggested that groups, friendships, and communities can grow far off that number. For instance, Facebook and Flickr offer groups that can have multiple administrators or "admins". Those admins can organise the group, manage it by inviting and excluding members.

The most critical block of the matrix is reputation block [36] [37]. It is the "extent to which a user can identify the standing of others, including himself, in a social setting" [6]. It is proposed in the self-concept [20] that reputation becomes a critical matter when it comes to the online persona and presence. The social media provides the platforms to cater to the needs in this block in many forms; ratings, likes, shares, comments, views, and ratings [38] [39].

III. DISCUSSION

In the contemporary era, social media outlets and their platforms are one of the most effective tools of communication. The numbers of users keep increasing and even with the privacy breaches and information getting out of hands, making the things "viral". The needs for the latest and most relevant content triggers millions of browsing and internet searches, just because people get the information quickly and easily due to the wide use of SNSs. However, social media is not just about the process of communication but also about satisfying the latent needs of the user. These needs cater the needs from a broad spectrum of needs.

The need for having a virtual presence leads to having a distinct sense of identity. This way user receives satisfaction in the form of having an online profile. The need of having relationships (virtual in this case) is coupled with needs belonging to a community or a group. The user feels the bond of that virtual relation by exchanging the information with those specific groups. These groups can be in the form of a personal or professional association. The user being part of that

satisfies that need of belonging. However, just being part of that group is not the end. The need to have a conversation (via different communication tools, e.g., Facebook Messenger, WhatsApp, Instagram) helps the user get the full benefit of that association; and satisfies the need for communication along the way. In this was the purpose of sharing is also sufficed.

Most importantly, the very design of SNSs attempts to help the user satisfy the need for reputation. This one can be regarded as one of the most ancient human needs. It entices the users to develop a behaviour that is considered attractive by their peers. As a reward for the efforts on this reputation, the user receives likes, comments, shares and subscriptions.

From the theories and various models presented in this paper, it is safe to say that growth in the social media industry and its innovation is a two-way process. The condition implies that it was not only the users need their latent needs to exhibit and get connected with people similar to them, but also, they require their social media outlet to voice their ideologies and concerns on the issues that were close to them. In addition to that, these social media applications kept improving, innovating, and evolving as reciprocity towards the increased interest in connectivity. The result can be extracted that behaviour of social media and popularity is a process of knowledge and activity co-creation.

All these features on the part of the user, powerfully engineered in the behaviour of users (human beings), the SNS and media outlets design and develop their platforms accordingly. However, it is just not about what happens from the user side. The social media platforms on their own, try to figure out what feature or functionality can spike the use of their platform. Research and development on the part of SNSs owners is another factor in deciding what is presented to the user. In the end, the most essential and critical factor in the design and development of SNSs and platform is the needs of the user. It is the user who designs the architecture of these websites knowingly or unknowingly.

Based on the model discussed above it can be concluded that rise and innovation in the domain of social media platforms is not just a two-way process but it supplies the means to its users for holding and propagating their ideas across the platforms. The continuous interaction and comparison of social media platforms help in improving the features and functionalities of social media.

IV. CONCLUSION

There are many factors involved in the design and development of social media one can argue that it can be due to the factors coming from the innate needs of the user that are powerfully engineered into the behaviour of human beings. Since the users of social media are primarily human beings, it is safe to say that human behaviour plays an essential part in deciding the outcome of that design. The study started with discussing Hallikainen's model, where the study divided the social media types by its functions. There is a particular value added to the user's experience, and that is the reason people keep using that, and even the number of users is increasing. It adds social value by allowing the user to form social bonds with different people in the groups and clubs available online.

When the user gets the leisure experience, it adds up the emotional value to the equation as well. The continuous flow of information regarding the areas of interest and hobbies provides epistemic value to the user. The user gets to plan, invite, and celebrate the main events of life; from birthdays to graduation, experiencing the conditional value of SNSs. Apart from value addition to the user's experience, study thoroughly discussed the honeycomb model and how it engages the user. The user receives a separate (and virtual) sense of self by creating a persona, forms (virtual) relationships associated with those personas and practices the humane functions like sharing and conversating. The matrix pointed out how the behaviour of the user dictates the paradigm of social media development and changes occurring in that. In the days to come, it is expected that more functionalities based on the latent needs (that is not latent anymore) of the users will arise. The behavioural scientists will keep working on these needs of the user because, in the end, it is the users who design and shape the architecture of SNSs, knowingly or unknowingly.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. S. Kang, "Understanding the role of an IT artefact in online service continuance: An extended perspective of user satisfaction," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 353-364, 2010.
- [2] D. Boyd, "Social network sites: definition, history, and scholarship," *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 16-31, 2010.
- [3] U. Pfeil, "Age differences in online social networking – A study of user profiles and the social capital divide among teenagers and older users in MySpace," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 643-654, 2009.
- [4] Statista, "Social Media Statistics," [Online]. Available: <https://www.statista.com/topics/1164/social-networks/>. [Accessed 04 April 2017].
- [5] H. Nolan, "New York Times 'social media editor' playing out exactly as suspected," [Online]. Available: <http://gawker.com/5270593/new-york-times-social-media-editor-playing-out-exactly-as-suspected>. [Accessed 04 April 2017].
- [6] H. Kietzmann, "Social media? Get serious! Understanding the functional building blocks of social media," *Business Horizons*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 241-251, 2011.
- [7] S. W. Jonathan A. Obar, "Social Media Definition and the Governance Challenge," *Telecommunication Policy*, vol. 39, no. 9, pp. 745-750, 2015.
- [8] E. Qualman, "Socialnomics: How Social Media Transforms the Way We Live and Do Business," *Choice*, vol. 48, no. 3, p. 555, 2010.
- [9] K.-Y. Lin, "Why people use social networking sites: An empirical study integrating network externalities and motivation theory," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 1152-1161, 2011.
- [10] M. L. Hyun Ju Jeong, "The Effect of Online Media Platforms on Joining Causes: The Impression Management Perspective," *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, vol. 57, no. 4, 2013.
- [11] E. W. Ngai, K. M. Ka-leung, S. S. Lam, E. S. K. Chin and S. S. Tao, "Social media models, technologies, and applications," *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, vol. 115, no. 5, pp. 769-802, 2015.
- [12] S. Grogor, "Design Theory in Information Systems," *Australian Journal of Information Systems*, pp. 14-22, 2002.
- [13] I. Ajzen, *Belief, attitude, intention and behaviour: an introduction to theory and research*, Sydney: Addison-Wesley, 1975.
- [14] Ajzen, "The Theory of Planned Behaviour," *Organisational Behaviour*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 179-211, 2011.
- [15] K. M. Sheldon, "What is satisfying about satisfying events? Testing 10 candidate psychological needs," *Journal of Personality and Social*

- Psychology*, vol. 80, no. 2, pp. 325-339, 2001.
- [16] C. Lampe, "A familiar Face(book): Profile elements as signals in an online social network," in *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, New York, 2007.
- [17] E. Katz, "The uses of mass communication: Current perspectives on gratifications research," *Sage*, pp. 19-32, 2007.
- [18] S. Mehdizadeh, "Self-Presentation 2.0: Narcissism and Self-Esteem on Facebook," *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 357-364, 2010.
- [19] G. Leflot, "Teacher-child interactions: relations with children's self-concept in second grade," *Infant and Child Development*, 2010.
- [20] D. G. Myers, *Social psychology*, NY: McGraw-Hill, 2010.
- [21] "Why People Use Social Media Platforms: Exploring the Motivations and Consequences," *Business Information Systems*, vol. 3, no. 13, pp. 9-17, 2006.
- [22] M. Kujala, "Value of information systems and products: understanding the users' perspective and values," *Information Technology*, vol. 9, pp. 23-39, 2009.
- [23] P. K. Anjala S. Krishen, "The generation of virtual needs: Recipes for satisfaction in social," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 5248-5254, 2016.
- [24] H.-F. Lin, "Determinants of successful virtual communities: Contributions from system characteristics and social factors," *Information & Management*, vol. 45, no. 8, p. 522-527, 2008.
- [25] David W. McMillan, "Sense of community: A definition and theory," *Journal of Community Psychology*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 6-23, 1986.
- [26] A. S. Krishen, "From Liking to Loyalty: The Impact of Network Affinity in the Social Media Digital Space," *CM SIGMIS Database: the DATABASE for Advances in Information Systems*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 30-42, May 2015.
- [27] D. Donthu, "Observations: The infomercial shopper," *Journal of Advertising Research*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 69-76, 1996.
- [28] R. Hanjun, "INTERNET USES AND GRATIFICATIONS: A Structural Equation Model of Interactive Advertising," *Journal of Advertising*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 57-73, 2005.
- [29] W. L. Korgaonkar, "A multivariate analysis of web uses," *Journal of Advertising Research*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 53-68, 1999.
- [30] R. A. Papacharissi, "Predictors of internet use," *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 175-196, 2006.
- [31] R. J. Palmgreen, "Uses and gratifications and exposure to public television," *Communication Research*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 155-180.
- [32] A. Kaplan, "Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media," *Business Horizons*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 59-68, 2010.
- [33] A. M. Kaplan, "The early bird catches the news: Nine things you should know about micro-blogging," *Business Horizons*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 105-113, 2011.
- [34] R. Dunbar, "Neocortex size as a constraint on group size in primates," *Journal of Human Evolution*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 469-493, 1992.
- [35] Ajzen, "From intentions to actions: a theory of planned behaviour," *Action Control: From Cognition to Behaviour*, pp. 11-39, 1985.
- [36] S. Wasserman, *Social Network Analysis: Methods and Applications*, New York: Cambridge University Press, 1994.
- [37] G. Paul, "Is the digital divide between young and elderly people increasing," *First Monday*, vol. 10, no. 10, 2005.
- [38] K. Stanislaw Saganowski, "Predicting Community Evolution in Social Networks," *Entropy*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 3053-3096, 2015.
- [39] Z. Papacharissi, *Toward a new(er) sociability: Uses, gratifications and social capital on Facebook*, Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge, 2011.

AUTHORS PROFILE

Muhammad Yousaf Mushtaq is working as Assistant Director (IT) in the Education Department as well as visiting Lecturer in The Islamia University of Bahawalpur for 15 years. He is PhD scholar in the Department of computer science & IT in The Superior College (University Campus), Lahore Pakistan. His research focuses on Human-Computer Interaction, Software Engineering and also interested in Data Science.

Muhammad Salman Mushtaq received a B.S. degree in Economics and a master's degree in marketing. In 2016, he started his master's degree in information technology from The University of Queensland. His postgraduate thesis is based on authentic e-learning education systems. Currently, Mr Mushtaq is providing consultancy in Brisbane CBD in Software Development and QA Testing industry. Mr Mushtaq is the recipient of UQ Employability Grant and UQ Employability Award. His research interest areas include the use of technology in health and education, IoT, number theory, ubiquitous computing, and machine learning.

Muhammad Waseem Iqbal Muhammad Waseem Iqbal is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Software Engineering at The Superior College (University Campus), Lahore, Pakistan. He has completed his PhD from The Superior College, Lahore. His research focuses on Human-Computer Interaction, Adaptive User Interfaces for Mobile Devices, Interfaces for Visually Impaired People, Semantic Relations & Ontological Modeling.

Syeda Mehwish Jamil is a psychologist and a researcher by profession. She completed her M.Sc. in psychology from National Institute of Psychology, Quaid-i-Azam University Islamabad. She is interested in researching human behaviour towards the SNSs and its influences.